

ECOLOGICAL RISK ASSESMENT FOR THE POPULATION LIVING IN NEARBY CITIES DUE TO THE ACTIVITIES OF LARGE AVIATION HUBS.

(Discuss about how many factors contribute to increased ecological risk)

Rostyslav Sipakov, Ph.D., Research director

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0862-5043> ross.s@uaecs.org

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Abstract. Aviation transportation is a significant contributor to the economy and an essential part of the global trade and travel system. (Kim et al., 2015) The number of cargo and passengers flying in and out of airports continues to rise. In 1930, the number of commercial airlines in operation was just 10 and they were using only about 300 aircrafts to fly around 9 million people per year as opposed to today's 3 billion passengers on 15 thousand planes worldwide. (Abraham, 2016) Fig.1. show the number of air traffic passengers traveling to or from the United States from 2006 to 2020.

The chemicals from jet engine exhausts contain high combustion by-products, leading to reproductive disorders, congenital disabilities, and cancers over long periods of exposure. The formation of carcinogens in the atmosphere is possible due to photochemical reactions leading to so-called secondary pollution. (Voloshkina et al., 2019) Studies have shown that the reaction rate in exhaust plumes is higher than in a typical environment. The chemical reactions continued after the exhaust plume was diluted to the normal state of the atmosphere several miles from the emission area. (Lee et al., 2011) In addition to polluting substances associated with vehicles, aircraft exhaust, or direct fuel emissions, the environment and public health also are exposed to ultrafine particles (UFP). (Merzenich et al., 2021)

Airports' effects on local air quality and public health are poorly studied. (Klemm et al., 2008) The existing research does not consider the factor of increased traffic of road transport within the boundaries of the aviation hub, the car rental companies' locations, parking spaces, and trucks. This research will assess chemical risks due to activities at busiest U.S. airports (Table 1). In this study, will discuss how many factors contribute to increased levels of chemical emissions in areas near airports, such as vehicle traffic and jet engine exhausts from airplanes taking off and landing.

Methods of the forecasting air and vehicles traffic demand using an econometric model. In the early 1970s, the United States and Europe were the industry's two main markets. The migration eastward began early in the century, aided by China's and India's rapid economic expansion. When Indians developed the same proclivity for travel as North Americans, the scheduled air transportation market alone increased to three billion people. There are many direct factors affecting global aviation. In particular, it is important to keep an eye on exogenous demand stocks, economic downturns, political and economic sanctions, competition, gross domestic product (GDP), supporting infrastructure, and macroeconomics stability. Using world aggregate time-series data from 1970 to 2005, the correlation coefficient between air transportation passengers and GDP is 0.99. For the year 2005, the correlation coefficient between air transportation passengers and GDP using cross-sectional data for 137 countries is 0.93. (Hansman and Ishutkina, 2009) There are various forecasting methodologies used in the airline sector to anticipate future air traffic volume.

In this study we will be focusing on econometric model because the econometrics differs both from mathematical statistics and economic statistics. Economic statistics do not provide explanations for the growth of various variables, nor do they provide measurements of the parameters of the connections. Statistical approaches may be inapplicable to economic phenomena since they do not fit inside the framework of controlled experiments. For example, in real-world trials, the variables frequently vary continuously and concurrently, making controlled trials ineffective. Econometrics allows us to employ statistical approaches after applying them to economic concerns. One of the most essential functions of econometrics is to provide tools for modeling based on supplied data. The regression modeling methodology comes in handy for this endeavor. Forecast from a simple linear regression model are easily obtained using the equation

$$y = f(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k) + \varepsilon$$

where f is well-defined function, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k$ are the parameters which characterize the role and contribution of X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k , respectively. The term ε reflect the stochastic nature of the relationship between y and X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k and indicates that such a relationship is not exact in nature. (Shalabh, n.d.)

Measurement's the chemicals from jet engine exhausts includes nitrogen oxides ($NO_x = NO + NO_2$), formaldehyde ($HCHO$), acetaldehyde (CH_3CHO), carbon dioxide (CO_2), ozone (O_3), particle number (PN), black carbon (BC) and other trace compounds. (Wuebbles et al., 2007) The chemical composition from vehicles engine exhausts is almost identical and is described in detail in the scientific work. by (Sipakov, 2021) The concentration of the above-indicated chemicals will be measured using ecochem photoelectric aerosol sensors. The research by (Sipakov, 2021) established a correlation relationship between the emissions of (C_xH_x) and meteorological conditions in the formation of secondary formaldehyde pollution. We will apply these methods of this study to determine the concentration of ($HCHO$) produced by photochemical processes from pollution sources associated with airport operations.

The air quality indicators PM2.5 and PM10 are not very sensitive markers for assessing the influence of traffic-related PM emissions on air quality since regional background concentrations dominate them. (Keuken et al., 2013) In this case we will focus on black carbon concentration that can be converted to elemental carbon (EC) concentrations. Black carbon concentration we will measure with a multi-angle absorption photometer. For monitoring we will define transects in the 3–10-miles range perpendicular to the direction of the prevailing winds at varying downwind distances. For this purpose, we will use the wind rose provided by NOAA Climate.gov. The planed average time for conduct the measurement is 10 days for each airport.

Conclusions. Accurate information about chemical risks for the population living in nearby cities due to a large aviation hub's activity will help create protective measures for the environment and public health. The obtained results of this research can use for creating inventories of the jet engine exhaust emissions.

Key words: Chemical risks, Jet engine exhausts, Ultrafine particles, Health, Econometric, Forecasting, Air pollution

Table 1

Busiest U.S. airports in 2019, based on the number of passengers enplaned (in millions).

#	Location and name of airport	Passengers
1	Atlanta GA (ATL)	53.86
2	Los Angeles, CA (LAX)	43.36
3	Chicago, IL (ORD)	41.01
4	Dallas, TX (DFW)	35.87
5	Denver, CO (DEN)	33.89
6	New York, NY (JFK)	31.13
7	San Francisco, CA (SFO)	27.87
8	Seattle, WA (SEA)	24.99
9	Orlando, FL (MCO)	24.79
10	Las Vegas, NV (LAS)	24.79
11	Charlotte, NC (CLT)	24.22
12	Newark, NJ (EWR)	23.23
13	Phoenix, AZ (PHX)	22.63
14	Houston, TX (IAH)	22.02
15	Miami FL (MIA)	21.48
16	Boston, MA (BOS)	20.73
Total		475.87

Sources by Bureau of Transportation Statistics / June 2020 / www.transtats.bts.gov

Fig.1. Total number of air traffic passengers traveling to or from the United States from 2006 to 2020 (in million passengers).

Sources by Federal Aviation Administration / March 2020 / FAA Aerospace Forecast 2020-2040, page 91

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